

length polymorphism (RFLP) gene dosage analysis (Acro4S^{4L}-a, Acro7a, Acro7b). To distinguish two Acro4S^{4L} isolated from different origins, the acrotrisomics were designated as Acro4S^{4L}-a and Acro4S^{4L}-b, and Acro7.

Acro4S^{4L}-a and Acro7a were selected in the F₁ plants; the other acrotrisomics were obtained from the progenies of primary trisomics. Acro4S^{4L}-a and Acro4S^{4L}-b each had a complete short arm (4S) and heterochromatin region of the long arm (4L) on chromosome 4 in addition to a normal chromosome complement as identified by mitotic chromosome analysis. RFLP gene dosage analyses were studied based on RFLP map (Saito et al 1991). RFLP gene dosage effects of Acro4S^{4L}-a were observed at the loci on *XNpb203*, *237*, and *311* but not at the loci on *XNpb49*, *114*, and *120* on chromosome 4. These plants had narrow grains, as did those of Acro4S^{4L}-b.

Acro5 had a fragment of about one-third of chromosome 5, and the plants had small grains and short panicles. RFLP gene dosage effects of Acro7a and Acro7b were observed at the locus of *XNpb338* but not at the loci *XNpb33* to *22* on chromosome 7. These plants had compact panicles and round grains. Acro11 had a fragment containing heterochromatin. Morphological features of the plants were late heading and short stature.

The acrocentric chromosome of each acrotrisomic was easily transmitted to the

Breeding behavior of acrotrisomics upon selfing.

Acrotrisomic	Plants (%)			Plants (no.)
	Disomics	Acrotrisomics	Primary trisomics	
Acro4S ^{4L} -a	55.2	35.8	9.1	618
Acro4S ^{4L} -b	61.9	37.1	0.9	854
Acro5	59.4	38.1	2.5	286
Acro7a	71.3	27.3	1.5	891
Acro7b	66.4	30.6	3.0	265
Av (total)	63.5	33.3	3.2	(2914)

next generation. The average frequency of acrotrisomics in the selfed progenies of five acrotrisomics was 33.3%, ranging from 27.3% in Acro7a to 38.1% in Acro5 (see table).

RFLP gene dosage analysis of Acro4S^{4L}-a suggested that the break point of the acrocentric chromosome was in the region between *XNpb311* and *49* (10.5 cM) on chromosome 4, and that the chromosome lacked the region from *XNph49* to *lg* on the long arm. These findings and integrated linkage map (Ideta et al 1992) revealed the orientation of the marker genes on chromosome 4 (see figure). The arrangement of classical and RFLP marker genes from the long arm are *lg-XNph120* - *114* - *d-11* - *49* - *311* - *237* - *203*.

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Construction of chromosome 4 map using acrotrisomic-Acro4S^{4L}-a: classical linkage map (left), RFLP linkage map (center), and ideogram of chromosome 4 (right).

^a Italicized numbers indicate RFLP markers.

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Molecular mapping of fertility-restoring gene *Rf3* in rice

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Cytoplasmic male sterility in WA-Zhen-shan 97 A (ZSA), a male sterile line widely used for developing hybrid rice in China, is caused by the interaction between wild abortive cytoplasm and two nuclear genes.

A series of near-isogenic lines (NILs) carrying different genotypes for restoration was developed by nine backcrosses to ZSA using IR24, a restorer line with two fertility-restoring genes, as the donor (Zhang et al 1994).

To tag the restorer genes, the set of NILs and the donor IR24 were used for randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) analysis. From a survey of 720 random primers, we identified six RAPD markers that were associated with one of the two restorer genes. Three of the six RAPD markers (OPK05-800, OPU10-1100, and OPW01-350) were used as probes. They were located on chromosome 1 in a population of doubled haploid lines derived from cross IR64/Azucena.

An F₂ population was developed from the cross between ZSA and ZSRR21. ZSRR21 is a NIL carrying two restorer genes. Thirty-six sterile plants in the F₂ segregating population were selected for linkage analysis. The three RAPD markers and three restriction fragment length

polymorphism markers (RG532, RG140, and RG458 located on chromosome 1) were found to be closely linked to the restorer gene. The distances between each of the six markers and the restorer gene were less than 4 cM in this population (see figure).

For fertility restorer genes in rice, *Rf1* was the notation given to the gene located on chromosome 10, which restores male fertility in line CMS-B (Shinjo 1975). *Rf2* was the notation given to the gene located on chromosome 2, which restores male fertility in line CMS-L (Shinjo and Sato 1994). In this study, the restorer gene located on chromosome 2, named *Rf2* in a previous paper, is named *Rf3* (Zhang et al 1994).

Location of the restorer gene *Rf3* on chromosome 1. The map was developed using the *F*₂ population of 36 sterile plants derived from the cross Zhenshan 97 A/ZSR21. Molecular markers are shown on the right side of the figure. Map distances (in cM) are based on the Kosambi function.

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Characterization of common *cis*-regulatory elements responsible for endosperm-specific expression of rice glutelin gene

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Glutelin is the major seed storage protein of rice, accounting for about 80% of total endosperm protein. Since glutelin genes are expressed only in maturing endosperm tissue and are regulated mainly at the transcriptional level, they provide excellent

model systems of regulation of tissue-specific gene expression.

Glutelin is coded for by a small multi-gene family composed of about 10 copies per haploid genome (Okita et al 1989, Takaiwa and Oono 1991, Takaiwa et al 1991). These genes are clearly classified into two groups—designated as GluA and GluB subfamilies—that share about 60-65% homology between members of each subfamily at the nucleotide sequence level (Takaiwa et al 1991). Comparison of the nucleotide sequence in the 5' flanking regions of six glutelin genes showed that the conserved sequences are restricted to the 13 bp of AACA motif around -70, the GCN4 motif around -160 and -90, and the GCAA motif around -350 from the transcriptional start site. Therefore, these motifs may be candidate for *cis*-regulatory elements controlling the endosperm-specific expression found in the glutelin genes.

To identify the common *cis*-regulatory elements responsible for the endosperm-specific expression of glutelin genes, the 5' and 3' nested deletions and internal deletions of the 5' flanking regions of the *GluB-1* and *GluA-3* genes were transcriptionally fused to either β -glucuronidase (GUS) or firefly luciferase (LUX) reporter genes. These chimeric genes were transferred into the tobacco genome via *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation system or into the rice genome using electroporation method. The GUS or LUX activities were assayed in maturing seeds.

The GUS reporter gene was expressed at high levels in the sub-aleurone layer of the maturing rice seed. Essential *cis*-regulatory elements governing the spatially and temporally specific expression of the glutelin genes were located within the first 437 bp and 245 bp of the promoter regions of the *GluA-3* and *GluB-1* genes, respectively (Yoshihara and Takaiwa 1995).

The AACA motif and the GCNA4 motif within the 100 bp of the 5' flanking region, common to all the glutelin genes, were the key elements determining endosperm-specific expression of glutelin genes. Deletion or site-specific mutagenesis of this proximal AACA motif remarkably reduced

promoter activities. The GCN4 motif also acted as a major *cis*-regulatory element determining the quantitative level. Each of these elements is necessary, but not sufficient, for endosperm-specific expression because tissue specificity is retained irrespective of the absence of each element. However, deleting the entire region, which includes both the AACA and GCN4 motifs, abolished seed-specific expression, suggesting that the synergistic interaction between both elements determines the endosperm-specific expression of the glutelin genes.

To confirm the significance of combining the AACA and GCN4 motifs to confer the endosperm-specific expression, the regions (-245 to -145, -113 to -40), including both motifs, were fused to the truncated (-90 to +9) or core (-46 to +1) CaMV35S promoter/GUS cassette, and then introduced into tobacco and rice. Although neither the AACA motif nor the GCN4 motif—by itself—is capable of enhancing the truncated promoter of CaMV35S promoter, their combination conferred the endosperm-specific expression. However, the combination failed to activate promoter activity of the core CaMV promoter.

The results suggest that the combination of two sets of AACA and GCN4 motifs or the combination of one set of these two motifs and the G-box motif is required for the endosperm-specific expression of the rice glutelin gene.

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